

DOI

Bahramova Z.Sh.

IDEALOGICAL ROOTS OF THE STUDY OF KANT'S PHILOSOPHY

Annotation. As a philosopher, Kant not only emphasized the activity of consciousness, the subject, but also tried to reveal the classical German philosophy more fully and to develop new methods. Perhaps for this reason, even though it has been more than two hundred years since Kant's death, today his theories and ideas are still considered as the most necessary source in the science of philosophy, serving as a practical and critical school for young philosophers.

Keywords: materialism, philosophy, spiritual influence, imagination, aesthetic concepts.

He tried to gradually remove the concepts of Karl Marx's historical materialism, materialistic dialectic and tradition, and to reveal the science of logic as a science. Later, his aspirations served as the basis for the development of philosophical traditions founded by A. Schopenhauer.

While studying the scientific works of Kant, we can see and witness that his works served as a basic source not only in the field of philosophy, but also in other fields of science. Mathematical scientists such as D. Hilbert and L. Bruver used to fall in love with Kant's conversation before creating something new in mathematics, and tried to get something new from it.

The most interesting part of the matter is that Kant's works, both during his lifetime and after his death, served both his friends and opponents alike as the basis for the development of ideology. Once upon a time, people who said that Kant and his works and knowledge will never be needed were seriously mistaken. Even the editor-in-chief, who once did not publish Immanuel's work in his journal, after some time went so far as to change his journal to a journal of the field in which Kant was active.

We mentioned several works written by Immanuel above. Most of these essays were related to the problems of several sciences, such as theoretical philosophy, aesthetics, ethics, ethics, and natural philosophy. Kant mentions that the basis of philosophy is science. Effectively using the methods of these sciences, Kant avoids the traditional one-sided view of philosophy, and in his views we can witness the juxtaposition of both sensualist and rationalist approaches.

At first glance, everything seems to be very easy, but what we are just reading and writing now is the content of the whole life of this one person, a great philosopher, hidden in these lines, between these writings are his fifty years, that is, half a century of research. as stated. As a clear proof of this, we can say that the scientist created his first independent philosophical theory only when he was fifty years old.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

He tried to learn something new in the work of any creator, any great scientist, it didn't matter if he was older or younger, his lineage, or even in which field or science he was a creator, they all of them were embodied only under the image of a "teacher - a great person from whom knowledge can be obtained".

Perhaps, it is precisely because of the above that Immanuel considered a number of great scientists, including Martin Knutsen, Christian Wolff, Leibniz, Newton, Aristotle, as teachers, and tried to continue their work in spirit. Among his teachers, he singles out the famous Greek philosopher Aristotle, who has a wide range of spiritual influence and taught philosophical-logical categories and doctrines of perception. also acknowledges his ideas.

In 1787, the philosopher wrote the treatise "Prolegomena for any future metaphysics" in order to make his conclusions more accessible to the general public. The treatise was distinguished from others by the fact that human beings have a priori abilities that are higher than theoretical intelligence, and that these abilities are not related to thinking, as described in previous theories, but to human beliefs and ideas related to his soul.

At first, in his youth, Kant believed that the principles of beauty had an empirical nature and could not be studied philosophically, but at the end of his career, he announced that he changed his opinion. Scientists study Kant's life and his activities in two big periods: pre-critical period and critical period.

The main reason for the conditional division of one activity into two is the change in the views of the philosopher, that is, the duality of his thoughts has arisen, as he has criticized the ideas he emphasized at first. For example, a scientist initially believed that with the help of the human mind, he can achieve things that others and he cannot know. He said that in order to achieve this kind of perfection, a person should clearly imagine all the difficulties before him and keep his spirit in a positive state without losing his mind.

Kant writes a work reflecting the idea of individual independence and freedom and calls it "Metaphysics of Morals". In the work, the interpretation of aesthetic concepts such as oriental beauty, humanity, and altruism characteristic of the peoples of the East is widely covered.

Well, it is natural that we have many questions, such as how did the work of Eastern scientists reach the hands of a Western scientist, why did Kant decide to study the cultural heritage of these nations. We all know well that the 9th-13th centuries were recorded in the history of Eastern countries under the name "Age of Great Translations".

During this period, the works of several scholars, such as Al-Biruni, Al-Fargani, Al-Khorazmi, Ghazali, Ibn Rushd, Al-Faroabi, who were recognized by world science, were translated into Latin and used in Western countries, Western science. widely spread throughout the world of science.

Kant was also familiar with this great cultural heritage of scientists directly and indirectly (Hume, Spinoza, Descartes). The development of translation allowed humanity to unite not only books, but also the opinions of people who do

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

not understand each other's literary language on science, encouraging them to think more and act.

At first Immanuel read and analyzed the works of these great people. Even some great thinkers are influenced by the ideas of bees, analyze and synthesize in their brains for several days, justify each idea and compare it with their own views.

Conclusion

Kant created not only aesthetics and ethics, but also feelings such as beauty and purity based on ideological imagination. According to Kant, imagination is a practical ability, and it is a huge and powerful force that can create something of a different nature from an existing source. Through its actions, a person's imagination and perception are awakened, he manifests various emotional states, and the ability of reflexive discussion arises in a person.

According to him, a person can achieve a suitable goal when he can combine the points of several activity centers such as his senses, mind, actions, and heart. In our opinion, every young generation today, not only students, but also pedagogues-teachers, should read his works and learn his thoughts.

References:

1. Kant. Works in German and Russian / Rep. ed. Nelly Motroshilova and Burkhard Tuschling. Moscow: Nauka, 1996–2006
2. Adamson Peter. Philosophy in the Islamic World: A Very Short Introduction. Oxford University Press. New York. 2015.-P.234
3. Ahmedova M, Yoldoshev S, Shomatov O. Indian philosophy. Eastern philosophy. Tashkent. 2006.-B.189.
4. Bozorov A. Moral views of Aristotle and Immanuel Kant. Tashkent. 1884.-B.78

WORDLY
KNOWLEDGE